

Thermodynamics of Iron-Ferron System

C. S. G. PRASAD, K. BALCHANDRAN & SAMIR K. BANERJI

Chemical Laboratories, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani (Rajasthan)

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The green coloured chelates formed by iron(III) with ferron have been investigated spectrophotometrically. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 chelates are formed at pH 1.5, 2.5, and 3.0 respectively. Stability constants at various temperatures have been evaluated in order to determine various thermodynamic functions as ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS . Effects of dielectric constants and ionic strength have been determined. Thermodynamic stability constants have also been reported.

The colour reaction between trivalent iron and 7-iodo-8-hydroxy quinoline-5-sulphonic acid, commonly known as ferron, has been considerably used as a standard method for the estimation of iron. Many investigators have employed spectrophotometric methods to study this reaction, with conflicting results. Kinya Ogawa and S. Musha¹, have reported that iron combines with ferron in the ratio 1 : 3. They have, however, indicated that their results were inconclusive. Dey and coworkers² have more recently observed that the molar ratio of the iron-ferron chelates is 1 : 2 in the same pH range. It was therefore thought profitable to study the thermodynamics of the system, in order to obtain more conclusive results.

The present work deals with the detailed investigations of different species formed when iron (III) reacts with ferron. The stepwise formation constants, thermodynamic stability constants, effect of ionic strength and temperature on the stability and the thermodynamics functions such as free energy of formation, entropy and enthalpy changes during the complex formation have been evaluated. The effect of the dielectric constants of the medium on the stability of the complex has been interpreted by studying the system in mixed solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of ferron was prepared from a purified sample of the sodium salt of 7-iodo-8-hydroxy quinoline-5-sulphonic acid (E.Merck) in double distilled water and the solution of iron was prepared by dissolving ferric chloride (E.Merck) in double distilled water. The iron contents of the solution was estimated by standard methods. Absorbance measurements were made on a Hilger Uvispec Spectrophotometer (model H 700-380) using 1 cm effective light path. The cell compartment was fitted with a water jacket through which water from a thermostat could be circulated to maintain a constant temperature. pH measurements were made on a Beckman pH meter (model H 2). All solutions were kept for thirty minutes to attain equilibrium.

RESULTS

Nature of the complex formed : Job's method of continuous variations³ was used to study the stoichiometry of the complexes at different pH values and the results indicate that three different species are formed in solution, depending upon the pH of the medium as indicated in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Composition	pH range
1 : 1	1.0 to 1.5
1 : 2	2.0 to 2.6
1 : 3	3.0

Evaluation of stability constants : The stability constants were determined by the molecular extinction coefficient method⁴. The values obtained for step-wise formation constants have been presented in Table 2. In order to obtain the thermodynamics stability constants

TABLE 2

Log K	pH	λ max
Log $K_1 = 3.45$	1.5	650 nm
Log $K_2 = 4.74$	2.5	600 nm
Log $K_3 = 4.55$	3.0	440 nm

the stability constants were evaluated at various ionic strengths and the results were extrapolated to zero ionic strength. These values were corrected for iron(III)-chloride association⁵ and have been presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Thermodynamic stability constants (20°) corrected for iron (III)-chloride association⁵

$$\text{Log } K_1 T = 3.22$$

$$\text{Log } K_2 T = 4.52$$

$$\text{Log } K_3 T = 4.25$$

$$\text{Log } K_T \text{ (overall)} = 11.99$$

Evaluation of thermodynamic functions : For the determination of entropy and the enthalpy changes during the complex formation, the stability constants were determined at various temperatures (Table 4). From the slope of the curve obtained by plotting log K against $1/T$, the enthalpy change of the reaction was calculated. Assuming this to be

TABLE 4

Temperature (°C)	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K_3
20	3.45	4.83	4.55
30	3.50	4.88	4.61
40	3.55	4.94	4.64

constants over a range of experimental temperatures the entropy change of the reaction was calculated using the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. The free energy change during complexation was obtained from the van't Hoff isochore. The results of these determinations at various temperatures have been averaged and presented in Table 5. The positive entropy and enthalpy changes clearly indicate that the stability of the complex is mainly due to the entropy change and that the reaction is endothermic.

TABLE 5

ΔH (kcal/mole)	ΔS (e.u.)	$-\Delta F$ (kcal/mole)
$\Delta H_1 = 2.07 \pm 0.05$	$\Delta S_1 = 22.9 \pm 0.01$	$-\Delta F_1 = 4.65 \pm 0.07$
$\Delta H_2 = 2.35 \pm 0.07$	$\Delta S_2 = 30.2 \pm 0.09$	$-\Delta F_2 = 6.52 \pm 0.04$
$\Delta H_3 = 1.51 \pm 0.08$	$\Delta S_3 = 26.4 \pm 0.11$	$-\Delta F_3 = 6.15 \pm 0.06$

Effect of the dielectric constant of the medium on the stability: In course of the attempts to find out the effect of the dielectric constant of the medium, on the stability of the complex, several different percentages of ethanol were used as mixed solvents. Some of the representative results are shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6

% Alcohol	Dielectric constant (D)	Log K
10	72.8	12.3
20	67.0	12.1
30	61.1	11.8
40	55.0	11.5
50	49.0	11.1

Though the nature of the spectrum does not change with the organic solvent the optical density decreases with increasing percentages of alcohol. In media with high percentages of alcohol, the ligands are very little dissociated, due to the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium and as a result the degree of complexation will also be lowered. The extinction coefficients values were found to be the same in aqueous as well as mixed solvents. It has been noted that a linear relationship is obtained when $\log K$ is plotted against $1/D$ (D , dielectric constant of the medium) and it seems reasonable to assume that the complexes should dissociate more with increase in the percentage of alcohol. The results obtained support this view.

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REFERENCES

1. K. Ogawa and S. Musha, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1959, **8**, 161.
2. A. K. Dey, *et al.*, *Chim. Anal.*, 1963, **45**, 124.
3. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
4. M. M. Jones, 'Elementary Coordination Chemistry'. Reinhold, New York, 1963
5. E. Rabinowitch and W. H. Stockmayer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 335.

